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IDT Preprocessing: Count-dependent weighting and photometric biases

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1. INTRODUCTION

This note gives the results of numerical experiments with $1/(N+c)$ -type weighting of the binned IDT counts. The following properties of the signal parameter estimates were considered:

- The actual variances of the phase estimates (first and second harmonics): How good is the estimator?
- The estimated phase variances: Does the inverse normal equations (NE) matrix represent the actual variances?
- The chi-square goodness-of-fit: Does it follow the appropriate chi-square distribution?
- The photometric parameters I0, I1, I2: Is it possible to correct for biases?

2. EXPERIMENTS

The purpose was to investigate weighted least-squares estimates of the five Fourier coefficients b_1 to b_5 for IDT counts sorted into 12 bins. For simplicity we assume an equal number of samples per bin, so that the expected number of counts in the i :th bin ($i = 0$ to 11) can be written

$$E(N_i) = I_i = b_1 + b_2 \cos(q*i) + b_3 \sin(q*i) + b_4 \cos(2*q*i) + b_5 \sin(2*q*i)$$

with $q = 2*\pi/12$. Bin counts N_i were simulated by means of a Poisson generator from the above model, using realistic 'true' values of b_1 to b_5 depending on the H-magnitude of the star. These values are shown in Table 1 for the different magnitude/background combinations considered.

TABLE 1. True values of the signal parameters b_1 to b_5 (counts/bin).

H-mag	background	b_1	b_2	b_3	b_4	b_5
6.0	70.0 Hz	716.38	600.16	0.0	235.78	0.0
8.0	70.0	141.16	116.62	0.0	45.814	0.0
10.0	70.0	36.290	27.560	0.0	10.827	0.0
11.0	70.0	22.057	14.630	0.0	5.7476	0.0
12.0	70.0	16.298	8.2016	0.0	3.2221	0.0
12.5	70.0	15.331	6.2498	0.0	2.4553	0.0
13.0	70.0	15.351	4.8099	0.0	1.8896	0.0
12.0	0.0	9.7638	8.2016	0.0	3.2221	0.0
12.5	0.0	7.4402	6.2498	0.0	2.4553	0.0
13.0	0.0	5.7261	4.8099	0.0	1.8896	0.0

For each of the 10 magnitude/background cases, four different weighting schemes were tried: first equal weight to each bin, and then weights proportional to $1/(N+c)$ for $c = 1, 5, \text{ and } 10$. In practice the weights must somehow be normalized to give reasonable estimates of the variances; in fact we seek to express the weight associated with N_i in the form

$$W_i = f(c, \langle N \rangle) / (N_i + c) \quad (c = 1, 5, 10, \text{ infinity})$$

where $\langle N \rangle$ is the actual mean number of counts per bin and $f()$ a normalizing function to be derived from the experiments. The case $c = \text{infinity}$ formally corresponds to equal weighting.

10,000 experiments (simulated bin counts + weighted LS solution) were made for each combination of magnitude/background and weight type (c). This number is sufficient to determine the sample variances and covariances with relative errors below 1%. In each experiment the following items were derived:

- the estimated b_1 to b_5 ;
- the inverse NE matrix for b_1 to b_5 ;
- the phase estimates $p_1 = \text{atan2}(b_3, b_2)$ and $p_2 = 2 * \text{atan2}(b_5, b_4)$;
- the photometric parameters $I_0 = b_1$, $I_1 = \sqrt{b_2^{**2} + b_3^{**2}}$, and $I_2 = \sqrt{b_4^{**2} + b_5^{**2}}$;
- the goodness-of-fit statistic $\chi^2 = \sum_i W_i (N_i - I_i)^{**2}$;
- the mean number of counts per bin $\langle N \rangle = (1/12) \sum_i N_i$.

From each ensemble of 10,000 experiments, a number of sample statistics were derived:

- the sample means and sample covariance of b_1 to b_5 ;
- the sample mean of the inverse NE matrices;
- the sample means and sample covariance of p_1 and p_2 ;
- the sample means of I_0 , I_1 and I_2 ;
- the sample mean and sample variance of χ^2 .

Ideally, one would like the sample statistics to behave as follows:

- the sample means of b_1 to b_5 should equal the true b_1 to b_5 (unbiased b_1 to b_5);
- the sample covariance of b_1 to b_5 should equal the mean inverse NE matrix (so that the latter is an unbiased estimate of the covariance of b_1 to b_5);
- the sample means of p_1 and p_2 should be zero (because the true b_3 and b_5 are zero), and their covariance should agree with the mean inverse NE matrix after the appropriate Jacobian transformation;
- the sample means of I_0 , I_1 and I_2 should equal their true values (b_1 , b_2 and b_4);

- the sample mean of χ^2 should equal the d.o.f. (= 7) and its sample variance should equal twice the d.o.f. (= 14).

3. RESULTS

3.1. Sample variances of the phase estimates

Table 2 shows the sample standard deviations of p_1 and p_2 relative to the Cramér-Rao limit (given in the second column). The C-R limit is of course never attained by these phase estimates, because it would correspond to an optimal combination of p_1 and p_2 , as well as an optimal weighting (inversely proportional to the true intensity, I_i).

TABLE 2. Sample standard deviations of p_1 and p_2 for different types of weighting, expressed in units of the Cramér-Rao standard deviation (given in the second column).

H-mag	C-R (rad)	first harmonic (p_1)				second harmonic (p_2)			
		c=1	c=5	c=10	c=inf	c=1	c=5	c=10	c=inf
6.0	.0152	1.078	1.078	1.078	1.091	1.373	1.369	1.373	1.531
8.0	.0348	1.090	1.079	1.058	1.095	1.409	1.384	1.412	1.532
10.0	.0747	1.112	1.112	1.107	1.116	1.455	1.472	1.467	1.586
11.0	.1097	1.168	1.137	1.122	1.131	1.572	1.563	1.534	1.637
12.0	.1673	1.195	1.199	1.185	1.171	1.866	1.826	1.797	1.878
12.5	.2116	1.275	1.236	1.249	1.216	1.880	1.904	1.908	1.918
13.0	.2729	1.384	1.374	1.322	1.313	1.871	1.817	1.844	1.852
12.0#	.1300	1.152	1.129	1.114	1.115	1.570	1.617	1.615	1.705
12.5#	.1489	1.163	1.134	1.130	1.120	1.647	1.652	1.684	1.818
13.0#	.1698	1.212	1.141	1.122	1.140	1.686	1.717	1.744	1.830
mean ratio =		1.183	1.162	1.149	1.151	1.633	1.632	1.638	1.729
uncertainty =		.003	.003	.003	.003	.004	.004	.004	.004

Remark: # = no background (cf. Table 1)

The difference in mean sample standard deviation between different weightings is surprisingly small. For p_1 , however, it appears that the unweighted estimate ($c = \text{inf}$) and the $1/(N+10)$ -weighting are definitely superior to $1/(N+5)$ or $1/(N+1)$. For p_2 , there is no significant difference between the estimates with $c = 1, 5$ and 10 , while the unweighted estimate is definitely worse. On the whole, $c = 10$ seems to be the best choice from the accuracy point of view.

3.2. Weight normalisation

In the above experiments, the weights were provisionally set to $W_i = 1/(N_i+c)$ for $c = 1, 5$, and 10 , and to $W_i = 1/\langle N \rangle$ for the unweighted case ($c = \text{inf}$). The parameter estimates (b_1 to b_5 , and p_1, p_2) are independent of how the weights are scaled, i.e., how the function $f(c, \langle N \rangle)$ is chosen. The inverse normal equations matrix is however inversely proportional to the weights, and the computed chi-square directly proportional. Accordingly, there are (at least) two different ways to choose the weight normalisation function $f(c, \langle N \rangle)$:

- the weights are scaled in such a way that the inverse normal equations matrix is a reasonable estimate of the covariance of b_1 to b_5 ; or
- the weights are scaled such that the sample mean of chi-square equals the d.o.f. (= 7).

Note that a simple scaling of the weights cannot in general give an inverse NE matrix which is an unbiased estimate of the covariance (since the matrix contains 15 different elements). The criterion used here to 'match' the inverse NE matrix to the sample covariance is simply the trace, i.e. the sum of the diagonal elements. Table 3 shows the weight correction factor (relative to the provisional weighting mentioned above) for the different weightings, calculated both from the trace of the inverse NE matrix, and from the chi-square statistic.

TABLE 3. Empirical correction factors for the different weightings, as computed from the trace of the inverse NE matrix and from the chi-square.

H-mag	<N> (typical)	1/(N+1)		1/(N+5)		1/(N+10)		1/<N>	
		trace	chi2	trace	chi2	trace	chi2	trace	chi2
6.0	716.	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.02	1.01	1.01	1.00	1.00
8.0	141.	0.99	1.01	1.03	1.04	1.08	1.09	0.99	0.99
10.0	35.8	0.99	1.03	1.12	1.17	1.29	1.33	0.99	0.99
11.0	21.7	0.98	1.04	1.20	1.26	1.48	1.53	1.01	0.99
12.0	16.0	0.99	1.05	1.29	1.34	1.62	1.67	1.00	1.00
12.5	15.0	0.98	1.05	1.30	1.35	1.66	1.71	0.99	1.00
13.0	15.0	0.98	1.05	1.28	1.34	1.67	1.68	1.00	1.00
12.0#	9.50	1.00	1.13	1.53	1.65	2.14	2.25	1.00	1.00
12.5#	7.21	1.02	1.16	1.72	1.85	2.51	2.61	1.00	1.00
13.0#	5.55	1.06	1.21	1.96	2.11	2.97	3.07	0.99	1.01
COEFF =		0.1	1.1	5.1	6.0	10.7	11.4	-	-

Remark: # = no background (cf. Table 1)

The experiments indicate that the provisional $1/\langle N \rangle$ weight adopted for the unweighted least-squares estimation is in fact quite accurate both for the trace and for the chi-square. For the $1/(N+c)$ weighting, we might then expect that the mean weight, which is approximately $1/(\langle N \rangle + c)$, would require a correction factor of

$$\frac{1/\langle N \rangle}{1/(\langle N \rangle + c)} = 1 + \frac{\text{COEFF}}{\langle N \rangle} = f(c, \langle N \rangle)$$

with $\text{COEFF} = c$. Empirically, we find that such a relation does indeed exist, albeit with a slightly modified coefficient. The bottom row of Table 3 shows the values of COEFF obtained by least-squares regression. These are in fact rather close to c , but there is a systematic difference between the values obtained from the trace and from the chi-square; for the latter, COEFF seems to be greater by one. (Could this be a profound result?) Clearly we cannot make both the trace and the chi-square unbiased (for finite c) by using a single normalisation function $f(c, \langle N \rangle)$. The difference is larger for small c and faint stars. For $c = 10$, the difference seems to be negligible and we might adopt $\text{COEFF} = 11.0$ as a compromise, but e.g. if $c = 1$ is chosen, one might use $\text{COEFF} = 0$ in order to compute the parameters and their covariance, and thereafter apply a correction factor of $1 + 1.1/\langle N \rangle$ only to the chi-square.

After weight normalisation, the sample variances of the chi-square statistic become close to the theoretical value (= 14), except for the $1/\langle N \rangle$ weighting, where the sample variances are usually somewhat large (about 16 to 18).

3.3. Correlation biases

With the weight normalisation derived in 3.3 the diagonal elements of the inverse NE matrix will be reasonable approximations to the variances of b_1 to b_5 . This is no guarantee however that the off-diagonal elements are in any way representative of the covariances. For instance, with equal weights (e.g. $W = 1/\langle N \rangle$), the NE matrix is practically diagonal; if its inverse is taken as an estimate of the covariance matrix, then this will predict zero correlation between any pair of parameters (and also between p_1 and p_2). This is manifestly false: in fact, the unweighted LS estimation generally gives stronger positive correlations (e.g. between p_1 and p_2) than any of the other weighting schemes considered here. Interestingly enough, the $1/(N+1)$ -weighting gives an almost unbiased estimate of the entire covariance matrix, while $c = 5$ and 10 give correlation estimates somewhere between the true values and zero, depending on the magnitude and background. Table 4 summarizes the true and estimated correlation between b_3 and b_5 (which is about the same as that between p_1 and p_2) for the different experiments; the 'true' values are taken from the sample covariance matrices.

TABLE 4. True and estimated correlation between b_3 and b_5 .

H-mag	c = 1		c = 5		c = 10		c = inf	
	true	est	true	est	true	est	true	est
6.0	.442	.431	.444	.428	.428	.425	.452	.000
8.0	.443	.422	.420	.409	.427	.393	.450	.000
10.0	.386	.381	.398	.339	.400	.298	.425	.000
11.0	.336	.324	.340	.271	.335	.227	.353	.000
12.0	.254	.241	.245	.192	.277	.154	.258	.000
12.5	.191	.193	.209	.152	.207	.122	.209	.000
13.0	.157	.150	.175	.117	.171	.094	.169	.000
12.0#	.428	.401	.446	.277	.451	.204	.461	.000
12.5#	.451	.391	.475	.249	.457	.175	.460	.000
13.0#	.442	.375	.474	.220	.461	.149	.464	.000

Remark: # = no background (cf. Table 1)

It can be noted that the correction factors $F = (\text{true corr})/(\text{estimated corr})$ are almost the same as the weight normalisation factors $f(c, \langle N \rangle)$ derived in the previous section. This indicates that a nearly unbiased estimate of the complete covariance matrix could have been obtained (for $c = 1, 5,$ and 10) by using the provisional weighting $1/(N+c)$, and then correcting only the diagonal elements of the inverse NE matrix through division by $f(c, \langle N \rangle)$, leaving the off-diagonal elements as they are. However, this would not necessarily preserve the positive definiteness of the matrix. Positive definiteness could on the other hand be guaranteed if instead only the diagonal elements of the Cholesky factor were modified (divided by the square root of the normalisation function). This has not been tried though.

3.4. Photometric biases

The diagrams show the biases in the photometric parameters I0, I1, and I2 plotted against the observed ratio I0/I1. The biases are defined in the sense

$$\text{bias} = (\text{estimated value}) - (\text{true value})$$

A simple linear relation to I0/I1 seems to hold for the biases of I1 and I2, while the bias of I0 rather seems to depend on I0 itself (or <N>, which is almost the same as the estimated I0 or b1). The relations derived are:

bias(I0) = -0.56	counts/bin	for c = 1
-0.55 + 1.79/<N>	counts/bin	for c = 5
-0.65 + 1.18/sqrt(<N>)	counts/bin	for c = 10
0.00	counts/bin	for c = inf
bias(I1) = -0.12 + 0.124*(I0/I1)	counts/bin	for c = 1
-0.22 + 0.146*(I0/I1)	counts/bin	for c = 5
-0.18 + 0.135*(I0/I1)	counts/bin	for c = 10
+0.02 + 0.074*(I0/I1)	counts/bin	for c = inf
bias(I2) = -0.20 + 0.335*(I0/I1)	counts/bin	for c = 1
-0.24 + 0.339*(I0/I1)	counts/bin	for c = 5
-0.17 + 0.303*(I0/I1)	counts/bin	for c = 10
-0.11 + 0.293*(I0/I1)	counts/bin	for c = inf

4. CONCLUSIONS

From the accuracy point of view, the $f/(N+10)$ or $1/<N>$ weightings are clearly to be preferred. (The 3 % difference compared with the $1/(N+1)$ weighting may seem to be small, but it is equivalent to 6 % extra dead time or almost two months of observation!) The $1/(N+1)$ weighting is otherwise very attractive, especially in that it gives such a good (unbiased) estimate of the covariance matrix. I think however that the accuracy aspect must have top priority in this case, and I would therefore recommend to try out the $f/(N+10)$ weighting in the more realistic simulations at RGO. (The equally accurate $1/<N>$ scheme should be discarded because of the very unrealistic covariance estimates, and perhaps also because of the too broad distribution of the chi-square statistic.)

The proposed procedure is then to use 12 bins for the IDT preprocessing, to compute the average number of counts per bin, <N>, and then apply a least-squares estimation of b1 to b5 using the following weight per bin:

$$W = \frac{1 + \text{COEFF}/<N>}{N + 10}$$

with COEFF = 11.0 (to be confirmed). This should give a reasonable variance of unit weight as well as a reasonable distribution of the chi-square statistic. Finally the estimates of the photometric parameters I0, I1 and I2 are corrected by subtracting the biases computed according to Section 3.4 (for c = 10). (The biases may be converted to counts/sample through division by the mean number of samples per bin.)

Bias in I0 (o), I1 (x), I2 (+); 1/(N+1)-weighting

Bias in I0 (o), I1 (x), I2 (+); 1/(N+5)-weighting

Bias in I0 (o), I1 (x), I2 (+); 1/(N+10)-weighting

Bias in I0 (o), I1 (x), I2 (+); 1/<N>-weighting

